

The Effects of Arts-And-Culture-Based Teaching on Upper Secondary School Students Performance Among Orang Asli Students in Perak

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of arts-and-culture-based instruction delivered through the Sedaya Module on the History achievement levels of indigenous (Orang Asli) Form Four students in Perak. The persistently low performance of Orang Asli students is often linked to conventional teacher-centred approaches that do not align with their learning preferences. The Sedaya Module was developed to address this pedagogical gap by integrating singing, educational drama, dance, music, visual arts, and handicrafts as culturally responsive learning strategies. A quasi-experimental design was employed involving a control group (n = 43) and a treatment group (n = 43) through pre-test and post-test administration. The instrument comprised 40 expert-validated objective items, and data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Findings indicate only moderate improvement in the control group, with no students achieving excellent grades. In contrast, the treatment group demonstrated substantial improvement, with 66.1% achieving high and excellent grades and a reduction in low achievers from 58.14% to 2.32%. This study provides early quantitative evidence supporting the effectiveness of an arts-based module designed specifically for Orang Asli students and highlights its potential for wider implementation in creative and multimodal learning environments.

Keywords: *Cultural arts learning; All Modules; historical achievements; Orang Asli students; Quasi-Experimental; multiple intelligence; Pedagogy based on cultural arts*

INTRODUCTION

History education plays a vital role in shaping national identity, fostering an appreciation of national heritage, and developing critical thinking skills among students. However, student achievement in this subject particularly within the indigenous (Orang Asli) communities remains at a concerning level. One contributing factor is the continued use of conventional teacher-centred instructional methods that rely heavily on textbook usage. Such approaches do not align with the learning tendencies of Orang Asli students, who respond better to visual, kinaesthetic, rhythmic, musical, and movement-based activities [1], [2]. Previous studies have also shown that arts-and-culture-based learning can enhance students' motivation, attention, and memory, thereby making the teaching process more meaningful and effective [3]. In response to this need, the Sedaya Module was developed as an alternative approach to strengthen History subject instruction by integrating cultural arts elements such as singing, educational drama, music, visual arts, and handicrafts. The module is grounded in Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences,

which emphasizes the role of artistic experiences, multisensory stimulation, and their connection to the construction of new knowledge.

However, empirical evidence on the effectiveness of arts-and-culture-based instruction in improving the History achievement levels of Orang Asli students remains limited. Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the effects of the Sedaya Module intervention on the history knowledge performance of Form Four Orang Asli students using a quasi-experimental design involving a control group and a treatment group. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to strengthening arts-based pedagogical practices in history education and to provide implications for curriculum development as well as teaching and learning (T&L) practices in schools with Orang Asli student populations.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The study of history plays a crucial role in shaping national identity, fostering critical thinking, and cultivating a sense of patriotism among students. However, the achievements of Orang Asli students in this subject remain low, as reported by the Ministry of Education (MOE). Previous studies support this finding, highlighting weaknesses in factual recall, conceptual understanding, and the ability to accurately interpret historical information. [4], [5]. This issue is further influenced by pedagogical factors, particularly the continued use of conventional teacher-centred approaches and the dominant reliance on textbooks in schools, including those with a majority of Orang Asli students [6], [7], [8]. Such teacher and textbook-centred approaches need to be reformed by creating teaching and learning experiences that are more engaging and enjoyable for students.

Traditional instructional methods such as chalk and talk have been found to be less effective for Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students, whose learning preferences are more inclined towards visual, kinaesthetic, movement-based, musical, and experiential activities[9]. Reliance on these traditional approaches often results in passive learning, limited student engagement, and an inability to connect historical content with their lived experiences. Previous studies also highlight that conventional approaches hinder Orang Asli students from mastering higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), writing historical facts coherently, and developing a deep understanding of historical events [10]. Therefore, such conventional practices must be transformed into more interactive teaching and learning approaches.

In the context of 21st-century learning, arts-and-culture-based pedagogy emphasizes the need to align instruction with students' cultural backgrounds, learning styles, and experiences. However, empirical evidence shows that teachers still make limited use of creative arts-based strategies that stimulate multiple senses and activate students' multiple intelligences. Arts-related approaches such as singing, educational drama, dance, music, visual arts, and handicrafts have been shown to improve memory, motivation, attention, and comprehension in History education (Pawanchik et al., 2010). Nevertheless, the systematic application of these approaches within structured learning modules for Orang Asli students remains significantly limited.

A significant gap in the existing body of research is the lack of empirical studies that quantitatively evaluate the effectiveness of arts-based learning modules on the History achievement levels of Orang Asli students. Although the Sedaya Module was developed to integrate cultural arts elements into history learning, its effectiveness must be systematically examined. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the impact of arts and culture-based instruction on the History achievement levels of Form Four Orang Asli students using a quasi-experimental design involving a Control Group and a Treatment Group.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effects of arts-and-culture-based instruction through the Sedaya Module on the History knowledge achievement of Orang Asli students for the topic *Proclamation of Independence*.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study was conducted to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify the level of History knowledge among Orang Asli students in the Control Group who follow conventional instruction.
2. To determine the level of History knowledge among Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students in the Treatment Group who follow arts and culture-based instruction through the Sedaya Module.
3. To compare the changes in History achievement levels between the Control Group and the Treatment Group before and after the intervention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review serves to situate the present research within a strong scholarly framework and to integrate it into the existing body of knowledge. Through this process, researchers are able to connect their study to established scholarship in a more systematic and meaningful manner [13]. Accordingly, this literature review was conducted to position the investigation on the effects of arts-and-culture-based instruction on the History achievement levels of Form Four Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students in Perak within a relevant academic context and to identify the need for such a study to be undertaken.

The academic achievement of Orang Asli students in Malaysia has consistently remained lower than that of mainstream students, particularly in the subject of history, which demands higher-order cognitive skills, factual mastery, and conceptual understanding [14]. Factors such as limited exposure to learning resources, disparities in access, and the unsuitability of conventional teaching approaches contribute to these learning challenges [15], [16], [17]. Previous studies have found that Orang Asli students tend to favour learning styles aligned with arts-and-culture-based activities such as singing, educational drama, dance, music, visual arts, and handicrafts, rendering traditional teacher-centred approaches less effective [18]. This underscores the need for culturally responsive teaching and learning approaches to enhance their engagement and achievement in history.

Arts-and-culture-based instruction encompasses the use of singing, educational drama, dance, music, visual arts and handicrafts to support the construction of meaning in the learning process. Previous studies have demonstrated that the integration of cultural arts can stimulate creative thinking, enhance long-term memory, generate positive emotional effects and strengthen conceptual understanding in [19], [20]. In Malaysia, this approach has been shown to improve students' motivation, attention and achievement in History, particularly when arts-based activities are integrated with local cultural contexts [21], [22]. This approach also aligns with the learning needs of Orang Asli students, who are more responsive to kinaesthetic, visual, movement-based, and musical learning experiences [23]. The pedagogical approach is further supported by a strong theoretical foundation, namely Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983).

Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences explains that each student possesses a unique profile of intelligences, encompassing visual-spatial, kinaesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal and verbal-linguistic intelligences [24]. These differences necessitate teaching approaches that are more flexible, holistic and not dependent on a single mode of delivery. In the context of History learning, students' understanding can be enhanced when teachers design activities that activate their dominant intelligences.

Arts and culture-based modules have a distinct advantage as they integrate multiple intelligences simultaneously. Activities such as singing, dance, educational drama, drawing and handicrafts not only make learning more enjoyable but also strengthen the process of meaning making. When students engage visually, kinaesthetically, musically, interpersonally, intrapersonal and verbally at the same time, they are able to connect historical facts with richer sensory experiences. The activation of multiple intelligences also enhances information encoding, thereby facilitating the recall of dates, figures and historical chronology. This approach is not only inclusive but has also been proven effective for learners with special needs as well as communities such as Orang Asli students, who are more responsive to experiential and culturally grounded learning.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employed a quantitative approach using a Quasi-Experimental design for the purpose of data collection and analysis. According to Noraini Idris (2013), quantitative research involves the process of gathering and analysing numerical data to describe, explain, predict, and control the phenomena under investigation. The Quasi-Experimental design is appropriate for evaluating the effectiveness of an instructional intervention through comparisons of two or more distinct sets of data [25]. In educational research, this design is frequently utilized because it is practical and applicable within authentic classroom settings [26]. In this study, respondents were divided into two groups: the Control Group and the Treatment Group. Both groups were administered a Pre-test to determine their baseline knowledge of the targeted History content. The diagram below provides a simplified illustration of the research design.

Figure 1: Quasi-Experimental Research Design

The teaching and learning process for History was conducted with respondents who met the criteria of the study. Once the sample was identified, students were divided into two groups: the Control Group and the Treatment Group. Both groups underwent a Pre-test to determine their baseline knowledge prior to the intervention. In a Quasi-Experimental design, the pre-test is essential as it provides the researcher with an initial understanding of the respondents’ cognitive levels and helps control existing variables between the groups.

The Treatment Group received instruction using the Sedaya Module, an arts-and-culture-based module that integrates singing, dance, music, educational drama, visual arts and handicrafts. Such integration of cultural arts has been shown to enhance students’ motivation, attention, engagement and information retention. The Control Group, on the other hand, received instruction through traditional teacher-centred methods commonly used in History teaching and learning.

After the intervention was completed, both groups were administered a Post-Test to assess their level of knowledge acquisition following the instructional treatment. A comparison of the pre-test and Post-Test scores was used to measure the effectiveness of the Sedaya Module, in line with Creswell’s (2018) recommendation that comparative analysis forms the basis for evaluating the impact of an intervention in experimental research [27]. The effectiveness of the intervention in this experimental research is evaluated by comparing two groups that were not randomly

assigned but were placed under strict control structures to ensure the validity of the findings.

RESEARCH RESPONDENTS

This study involved a total of 86 Form Four students from two schools located in two different districts in the state of Perak. The districts involved were the Kampar District and the Batang Padang District, which served as the study sites. The respondents were then assigned to the Control Group and the Treatment Group in accordance with the requirements of the Quasi-Experimental design.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

In this study, an objective-type achievement test was used as the main instrument to collect data through the administration of the Pre-test and Post-Test. The development of both instruments was carried out systematically, beginning with the identification of constructs, the preparation of the Table of Specification (TOS), the determination of item difficulty levels, and the construction of test items aligned with the content standards and learning standards of the Form Four History KSSM syllabus. The instrument then underwent a validation and reliability evaluation process by a panel of experts to ensure that each item demonstrated high levels of suitability, accuracy and consistency with the intended learning objectives.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURES

At the initial stage of the study, the Pre-test instrument was administered to both the Control Group and the Treatment Group to obtain baseline data prior to the implementation of the intervention. The Pre-test served to determine students' prior knowledge of the selected topic and to ensure that valid comparisons could be made after the intervention was conducted. Subsequently, the intervention phase was carried out by implementing the Sedaya Module an arts and culture-based module with the Treatment Group. The Control Group, on the other hand, received existing conventional instruction commonly practised in History teaching and learning. Once the instructional sessions for both groups were completed, the Post-Test was administered to all students. The Post-Test data were then compared with the Pre-test data to determine the effectiveness of the Sedaya Module in enhancing the History knowledge of Form Four Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis in this study was carried out quantitatively using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), supported by basic computational procedures in Microsoft Excel. To address the first research question, descriptive analysis was employed to describe the levels of knowledge and interest among Orang Asli students in both the Control Group and the Treatment Group. This analysis involved calculating percentages, mean scores, standard deviations, frequencies, and determining achievement levels based on the Malaysian Examinations Council (MPM) grading system for the SPM History subject. Through these descriptive analyses, the Pre-test and Post-Test data were translated into clear statistical indicators

that illustrate patterns of improvement or changes in students' knowledge and interest following the implementation of the Sedaya Module.

Descriptive analysis is crucial in providing an initial overview of students' performance patterns before inferential analysis is conducted. In addition, this analysis helps identify baseline differences between the Control and Treatment Groups, thereby supporting accurate interpretation of the intervention's effectiveness within the quasi-experimental framework.

RESEARCH FINDING

The findings of this study address the research questions outlined earlier. The first research question examines the level of History knowledge among Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students in the Control Group who received existing conventional instruction. The second research question identifies the level of History knowledge among Orang Asli students in the Treatment Group who were taught using the arts-and-culture-based Sedaya Module. Finally, the study compares the changes in achievement between the Control Group and the Treatment Group before and after the intervention was implemented.

Findings for Research Question One

The level of knowledge in the Control Group was obtained through the administration of the Pre-test and Post-Test. The Pre-test was conducted before the History lessons began using the existing conventional method and textbook-based instruction. The Post-Test, on the other hand, was administered after the History lessons were completed using the same instructional approach. The following are the findings obtained;

Table 1
Level of Knowledge of the Control Group for the Pre-test and Post-Test

Grade	Pre-test			Post-Test	
	Mark	<i>f</i>	Pct. (%)	<i>f</i>	Pct. (%)
A+ (High Distinction)	80-100	0	0.00	0	0.00
A (Mid Distinction)	71-79	0	0.00	0	0.00
A- (Low Distinction)	62-70	0	0.00	0	0.00
B+ (High Credit)	57-61	0	0.00	5	11.63
B (Low Credit)	50-56	0	0.00	1	2.32
C+ (High Merit)	45-49	3	6.98	7	16.28
C (Low Credit)	35-44	12	27.91	19	44.19
D (Pass)	30-34	4	9.30	5	11.63
E (Low Pass)	25-29	11	25.58	2	4.65
G (Fail)	0-24	13	30.23	4	9.30
Total	100	43	100	43	100

Figure 2
Comparison of Pre-test and Post-Test Results in the Control Group

The analysis indicates that the level of historical knowledge among students in the Control Group during the Pre-test was generally moderately low. None of the students attained higher-level grades such as High Distinction (A+), Mid Distinction (A) or Low Distinction (A-). Instead, the majority clustered within the lower-grade categories. The highest frequencies were recorded in Low Credit (C; 35-44 marks) with 12 students (27.91%), followed closely by Fail (G; 0-24 marks) with 13 students (30.23%) and Low Pass (E; 25-29 marks) with 11 students (25.58%). These results reveal that, prior to instruction, students displayed weak mastery of historical facts and concepts, with more than half falling within the Low Pass or Fail categories.

Following the implementation of the conventional instructional approach, the Post-test results showed a noticeable improvement in the overall grade distribution of the Control Group. Although no students achieved upper-level grades such as A+, A, or A-, there was a positive shift in the middle-performance bands. The number of students obtaining Low Credit (C) increased from 12 (27.91%) to 19 (44.19%), reflecting better comprehension of the content delivered. Additionally, students began achieving grades that were completely absent during the Pre-test, including High Credit (B+) with 5 students (11.63%), Low Credit (B) with 1 student (2.32%), and High Merit (C+) with 7 students (16.28%).

Despite these improvements, some students continued to remain in the lower performance categories in the Post-Test, such as Fail (G; 4 students, 9.30%) and Low Pass (E; 2 students, 4.65%). This trend suggests that, while conventional teaching methods helped strengthen basic understanding, the gains were relatively limited and did not translate into high levels of mastery. Overall, the findings indicate that traditional instructional approaches produced modest progress but were not sufficiently effective in elevating Orang Asli students to higher achievement levels, particularly in mastering historical knowledge.

9.2 Findings for Research Question Two

The level of knowledge in the Treatment Group was obtained through the administration of the Pre-test and Post-Test. The Pre-test was conducted before the

History lessons began using the existing instructional approach. The Post-Test, on the other hand, was administered after the History lessons were delivered using the Sedaya Module, which applies arts-and-culture-based learning. The findings are presented as follows:

Table 2
Level of Knowledge of the Treatment Group for the Pre-test and Post-Test

Grade	Pre-test			Post-Test	
	Marks	f	Pct. (%)	f	Pct. (%)
A+ (High Distinction)	80-100	0	0.00	3	6.98
A (Mid Distinction)	71-79	0	0.00	8	18.60
A- (Low Distinction)	62-70	0	0.00	5	11.63
B+ (High Credit)	57-61	0	0.00	4	9.30
B (Low Credit)	50-56	0	0.00	11	25.58
C+ (High Merit)	45-49	2	4.65	3	6.98
C (Low Credit)	35-44	13	30.23	6	13.95
D (Pass)	30-34	3	6.98	2	4.65
E (Low Pass)	25-29	13	30.23	1	2.32
G (Fail)	0-24	12	27.91	0	0.00
Total	100	43	100	43	100

Figure 3
Comparison of Grade Scores for the Pre-test and Post-Test of the Treatment Group

The descriptive analysis for the Treatment Group shows a substantial improvement in the History knowledge of Orang Asli students following the implementation of the Sedaya Module. Based on the Pre-test results, the majority of students were positioned within the lower achievement categories. Most students obtained Low Credit (C; 30.23%), Low Pass (E; 30.23%), and Fail (G; 27.91%), while only a small proportion achieved intermediate levels such as High Merit (C+; 4.65%) and Pass (D; 6.98%). No students achieved higher-level grades-High Distinction

(A+), Mid Distinction (A), or Low Distinction (A-)-indicating that the cohort demonstrated weak mastery of historical concepts and factual understanding prior to the intervention.

Following the implementation of the Sedaya Module, the Post-test results revealed a highly encouraging and substantial upward shift in student performance. A notable number of students achieved higher-level grades that were previously unattainable in the Pre-test. Specifically, 3 students (6.98%) achieved High Distinction (A+), 8 students (18.60%) achieved Mid Distinction (A), and 5 students (11.63%) achieved Low Distinction (A-). This emergence of top-tier grades represents a remarkable improvement, as none of these categories appeared during the Pre-test phase. In addition, High Credit (B; 25.58%) recorded one of the highest frequencies in the Post-test, signalling strong gains in conceptual understanding and historical knowledge mastery.

Conversely, the proportion of students in the lower achievement categories declined sharply. For example, Low Pass (E) decreased dramatically from 30.23% to 2.32%, and no students remained in the Fail (G) category in the Post-test. This reduction suggests that the Sedaya Module not only elevated overall achievement but also successfully supported low-performing students, enabling them to progress out of the lowest proficiency bands.

Overall, the findings for the Treatment Group demonstrate that the Sedaya Module had a highly positive and transformative impact on enhancing the History knowledge of Orang Asli students. The arts- and culture-based learning strategies embedded within the module provided meaningful, contextualised, and engaging learning experiences that fostered deeper understanding of historical concepts. The significant shift from predominantly low-achievement grades to the emergence of Distinction-level performance provides strong empirical evidence of the module's effectiveness as an alternative pedagogical approach for teaching History to Orang Asli students.

9.3 Finding for Research Question Three

The comparison of knowledge levels between the Control Group and the Treatment Group demonstrates a clear difference in performance improvement following the intervention. Both groups began at nearly the same starting point based on the Pre-test results, where the majority of students in both groups fell within the moderately low and low achievement categories. In the Control Group, the dominant grades were Credit (C; 27.91%), Low Pass (E; 25.58%), and Fail (G; 30.23%), while the Treatment Group showed a similar pattern with Credit (C; 30.23%), Low Pass (E; 30.23%), and Fail (G; 27.91%). No students in either group achieved higher level grades, confirming that the initial knowledge levels were low and comparable across groups.

However, the Post-Test results reveal a clear and substantial difference between the Control Group and the Treatment Group in terms of performance improvement. In the Control Group, improvement did occur, but at a moderate level. Some students achieved higher grades such as High Credit (B+; 11.63%), Credit (B; 2.32%), and High Pass (C+; 16.28%); however, the majority remained within the mid-achievement category, particularly Pass (C; 44.19%), while a small number continued to fall within the lower categories, including Minimum Pass (E; 4.65%) and Fail (G; 9.30%). This indicates that conventional teaching methods were only capable of producing moderate gains without generating substantial improvement in learning outcomes.

In contrast, the Treatment Group experienced far more significant improvement after receiving the Sedaya Module intervention. The Post-Test results show a major shift in achievement patterns, with students beginning to obtain high-level grades such as Highest Distinction (A+; 6.98%), High Distinction (A; 18.60%),

and Distinction (A-; 11.63%), none of which were present in the Pre-test. Moreover, Credit (B; 25.58%) became the largest category, reflecting stronger mastery of historical concepts among Treatment Group students. At the same time, lower-achievement grades such as Fail (G; 0.00%) and Minimum Pass (E; 2.32%) declined sharply, indicating that the Sedaya Module effectively supported low-performing students in improving their understanding.

Overall, the comparative findings demonstrate that the Treatment Group achieved substantially greater performance gains than the Control Group. Instruction supported by the arts-and-culture-based Sedaya Module proved to be far more effective in enhancing the History knowledge of Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students compared to traditional teaching approaches. The module not only elevated students' achievement across moderate and high categories but also significantly reduced the number of students in the lower-performance range. The marked differences between the two groups provide strong evidence that a more contextualised, culturally grounded and multimodal instructional approach such as the Sedaya Module can generate meaningful and significant positive impacts on History learning among Orang Asli students.

DISCUSSION

The discussion of this study's findings encompasses three key aspects: the level of History knowledge among Orang Asli (Orang Asli) students in the Control and Treatment Groups, and the comparative changes in achievement between the two groups. These aspects were analysed comprehensively by integrating the study's results with relevant theoretical perspectives and supporting literature.

The Pre-test findings for the Control Group indicate that the majority of students demonstrated a low level of History knowledge. This finding is consistent with previous studies which report that Orang Asli students often face difficulties in mastering History due to the continued reliance on conventional, teacher-centred instructional approaches [28], [29]. The dominance of the chalk-and-talk method does not align with the preferred learning styles of Orang Asli students, who tend to engage more effectively with visual, kinaesthetic, musical, and movement-based activities.

Effective learning requires instructional approaches to be adapted when existing methods or lesson planning do not correspond to students' learning characteristics [30]. The mismatch between passive conventional instruction and the experiential learning tendencies of Orang Asli students who value learning that sustains and reflects their indigenous knowledge has hindered the development of deep conceptual understanding in History. Consequently, this misalignment constrains students' cognitive development and classroom motivation [31]. In this context, students' prior knowledge and lived experiences represent intrinsic factors that naturally motivate Orang Asli students to engage with History learning [32]. These internal factors should therefore be prioritised in instructional design to enhance students' understanding and mastery of History content.

The modest improvement observed in the Control Group's Post-Test supports the argument by Dong *et al.* (2020), which states that traditional teaching approaches

only yield minimal gains and rarely facilitate higher levels of mastery. In addition also emphasise that one-way instructional delivery does not encourage the formation of strong cognitive connections, resulting in History learning that remains largely rote-based [33]. These findings reinforce the need for pedagogical transformation towards more interactive, contextual and arts-based learning approaches [6], as part of efforts to make History lessons more engaging and meaningful.

In contrast, the findings for the Treatment Group demonstrate substantial improvement following the implementation of the Sedaya Module. Students who initially scored in the lower categories in the Pre-test achieved significantly higher grades in the Post-Test. This dramatic increase is consistent with prior studies showing that arts-based instructional integration can stimulate memory, enhance motivation and support students in connecting new knowledge with prior experiences [34], [35], [36]. These results confirm that arts and culture-based approaches not only enhance factual mastery but also strengthen cognitive processes through active participation, multi-sensory engagement and more meaningful learning contexts outcomes that conventional methods are unable to produce.

The Sedaya Module activates multiple intelligences such as linguistic, visual-spatial, kinaesthetic and musical, in alignment with Gardner's (1983) Multiple Intelligences Theory. Literature further highlights that arts activities-including singing, drama, dance and visual arts-not only support students in remembering historical chronology but also foster empathy and help construct mental representations of historical events [37], [38]. These findings are further supported by studies demonstrating that arts-based approaches improve engagement, focus and integration of new information in History learning [39], [40], [41]. Orang Asli students in particular benefit significantly when learning is integrated with culturally familiar elements. Thus, this study strengthens the argument that the Sedaya Module serves as a meaningful and culturally responsive pedagogical intervention capable of enhancing History learning among Orang Asli learners.

The comparison between the two groups shows a distinctly wider improvement gap in favour of the Treatment Group, clearly indicating the effectiveness of the Sedaya Module. Although both groups began with similar baseline knowledge, the Treatment Group's performance post-intervention far exceeded that of the Control Group. This aligns with Bryce and Blown's (2024) assertion that significant conceptual growth occurs when learners are able to connect prior knowledge with new information through interactive and meaningful learning strategies [42]. The Sedaya Module provides such opportunities through arts-based activities and collaborative experiences that support concrete and visual assimilation of historical content.

Furthermore, previous research highlights that Orang Asli students often face challenges in mastering History when learning lacks cultural relevance and contextual connection [43]. The Sedaya Module addresses this gap by integrating elements of cultural arts into classroom instruction, consistent with the principles of culturally responsive teaching. Its demonstrated effectiveness also contributes to filling a gap identified in the literature namely, the lack of quantitative empirical studies on arts-based interventions tailored specifically for Orang Asli students.

In conclusion, the Sedaya Module not only significantly improves student achievement but also offers a pedagogical approach that is theoretically grounded and culturally responsive. These findings carry important implications for research and practice in Orang Asli education, highlighting the potential of arts-and-culture-based interventions to transform History learning experiences and outcomes for Orang Asli students.

Implications and Study Recommendations

This study was conducted to assess the level of history knowledge among Orang Asli students who received instruction using conventional teaching methods, evaluate the knowledge level of students who participated in the Sedaya Module intervention based on arts and culture, and compare the achievement changes between the two groups. Based on the empirical findings, several important implications can be outlined involving theoretical, pedagogical, and educational policy aspects. These implications not only support the objectives of the study but also strengthen the need for pedagogical transformation to enhance the quality of history learning among Orang Asli students.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings reinforce Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983), which posits that students learn differently through visual, musical, kinaesthetic, interpersonal, and verbal intelligences. The significant improvement observed in the Treatment Group demonstrates that instruction activating multiple intelligences simultaneously can strengthen historical understanding and improve academic performance. This suggests that integrating arts and cultural elements enhances memory retention, promotes meaningful learning, and effectively connects historical content with the cultural background and lived experiences of Orang Asli students, making learning more relevant and contextual.

The second implication concerns classroom instructional practices. The moderate improvement within the Control Group indicates that conventional methods still hold foundational value in teaching and learning; however, their effectiveness is limited, particularly for students who require visual and kinaesthetic stimulation. In contrast, the substantial improvement in the Treatment Group affirms that arts-based activities such as singing, dancing, educational drama, music, visual arts, and crafts not only help students comprehend historical facts but also increase their motivation, focus, and active engagement. Therefore, this study implies that history teachers are encouraged to incorporate arts and cultural elements to ensure more engaging and effective instruction, especially for Orang Asli students who are more responsive to experiential forms of learning.

From an educational policy perspective, this study provides significant implications for enhancing the education of Orang Asli students, who have long faced a substantial academic achievement gap. The Sedaya Module, grounded in arts and cultural elements, is systematic and easily adaptable for schools with Orang Asli student populations. This supports previous research recommendations emphasizing that teaching and learning approaches for Orang Asli students must consider their sociocultural backgrounds to improve academic performance. Therefore, the findings of this study may serve as a foundation for formulating micro-level policies at the

school level and macro-level policies at the ministerial level, aimed at strengthening the curriculum, teacher training, and the development of more inclusive and culturally responsive teaching modules.

As a recommendation, the arts-and-culture-based Sedaya Module could be expanded to mainstream secondary schools for students of all ethnic backgrounds. This approach has demonstrated the potential to enhance engagement, motivation, and conceptual understanding through arts-based activities such as singing, dancing, educational drama, music, visual arts, and crafts. Mainstream students also exhibit diverse learning styles that necessitate more creative approaches to deepen their mastery of History. Its implementation may be tailored to each school's context through teacher training, the provision of supporting modules, and integration into annual teaching plans. This strategy has the potential to create History lessons that are more interactive, enjoyable, and meaningful for all students.

Conclusion

Overall, the findings of this study indicate that arts-and-culture-based instruction through the Sedaya Module not only enhances the History knowledge of Orang Asli students but also contributes to the strengthening of learning theories and the development of more effective pedagogical practices. This study demonstrates that arts-based instructional innovations deserve serious attention as a means to reduce educational disparities and to improve the quality of History learning among Orang Asli students in Malaysia.

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